

POLICY BRIEF

LEARN FROM CITIZEN SCIENCE AND CLEAN OUR OCEANS OF PLASTICS

How citizen science can inform the European Commission's evaluation of the Single Use Plastic Directive.

In a Nutshell

The EU has taken decisive actions to reduce plastic pollution, including the adoption of the Single-Use Plastics Directive (SUP). However, the implementation of the SUP Directive faces a major challenge: monitoring and enforcement. Uneven surveillance, limited data and cross-border circulation hinder the Directive's full effectiveness. Citizen generated data has proven to be a key complement to official monitoring, providing broad spatial coverage, cost-effective data collection, and rapid reporting.

Policy context

Plastic pollution has become a pressing global environmental issue due to its widespread impacts on marine ecosystems and human health. It is addressed directly and indirectly in several Sustainable Development Goals, and the European Union (EU) is tackling the challenge via multiple legislative instruments, including the Single-Use Plastics Directive.

This directive is currently under evaluation. The European Commission is assessing how it has been implemented across EU Member States, the effectiveness of measures introduced in 2019, and whether the legislation remains fit for purpose.

Policy challenge

Monitoring compliance forms a critical challenge for the successful implementation of the measures introduced by the Directive in 2019.

EU Member States have differing and often limited monitoring capacities; market surveillance is uneven, and the lack of harmonised data on single-use Plastic (SUP) consumption and litter make it difficult for the European Commission to assess the effectiveness of the Directive.

The central question is how to strengthen monitoring and enforcement to support evidence-based evaluation and identify policy gaps.

Communities can make a difference

Citizen science can be part of the solution. It has become a critical approach for monitoring single-use plastics in marine environments across Europe. For instance, Marine Litter Watch is a citizen-based platform that helps fill data gaps in beach litter monitoring required by the Marine Strategy Framework Directive.

The benefits of citizen-generated data are threefold:

- It raises public awareness.

- It provides information on plastic composition, sources, and hotspots.
- It helps track compliance and policy effectiveness, for example by observing banned items such as single-use plastic cutlery or straws still present in public spaces, restaurants, or beaches.

Citizen science should be acknowledged as a key contributor to policy success, thanks to its broad spatial coverage, low cost, and rapid data collection.

Course of Action

Data on banned items

The SUP Directive does not require Member States to report quantities of banned items, creating an evidence gap that limits compliance checks and evaluation of the Directive. The European Commission could consider introducing such an obligation. Citizen science can help national authorities fill this gap through monitoring of beaches, rivers and urban areas for banned items, documenting them with photos and geolocation, and tracking trends to assess bans and guide enforcement.

A mention of such a role in the Directive would strengthen their recognition in EU Member States.

Enforcement gap

Citizen generated data show that banned products continue to circulate in EU Member States. These products are found notably in small shops. Unsurprisingly, cross-border and online trade aggravate the situation, making market surveillance and enforcement very challenging. This problem is not unique to the SUP Directive. However, given the large quantities of products falling under its scope and their significant environmental impact, more4nature believes action is needed.

The European Commission should examine the problem of continuing circulation of banned plastic items and assess options to address it to ensure compliance with the Directive.

Voices on the ground

 Ireland

Keelan & Iker Arenzana King
Regional Coastwatch
Coordinators for county Louth

As citizen scientists, how would you improve the directive?

“Litter requires a systemic, multi-faceted approach. While passing the SUP legislation is highly positive, we believe that a larger net should be cast at other forms of litter we are consistently finding on shores and estuaries: coffee cups, disposable vapes, aquaculture litter, polystyrene boxes, and legacy items. Specifically, an extension of existing extended producer responsibility schemes could be explored in the future for items such as nets, fisherman’s gloves, plastic fibres and tires.”

Reach out to us!

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